

Identification of Religious and Cultural Elements in Arts Learning Materials at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and Mosque Syuhada Kindergarten

Joko Pamungkas¹, Adi Dieni Maulana Rizka²

^{1,2}Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta

Corresponding Author: Joko Pamungkas joko_pamungkas@uny.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Religious Elements, Cultural Elements, Art Learning, Children

Received : 6, November

Revised : 20, December

Accepted: 29, January

©2024 Pamungkas, Rizka(s): This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research aims to describe religious and cultural elements in art learning materials in kindergarten. Art learning in early childhood is often carried out to develop various aspects of intellectual, social and spiritual maturity. This can be supported by the school's background under a religious foundation so that the learning carried out can be adapted to the existence of a religious environment in each school. The two schools use different cultural and religious elements in art learning at school. The writing of this article is the result of observations, interviews and documentation carried out using qualitative research methods with triangulation of data sources. The data analysis carried out obtained the results that the religious elements that appeared in arts learning in the two kindergartens were religious stories, religious singing, prayer activities with tunes, projects through stories in books, dancing with religious songs, playing angklung with spiritual songs, and playing gamelan with religious songs such as prayers. Meanwhile, the cultural elements applied are the introduction of traditional musical instruments, the introduction of traditional dance, the singing of children's songs, the use of traditional games associated with learning, making batik, and the use of traditional clothing in art learning.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the things that is very important for human life. This is in line with the description which states that education is the main factor in developing a quality society (Adini et al., 2022). This education can be started from an early age (Eka Retnaningsih & Patilima, 2022). Therefore, kindergartens emerged which can help children to develop all aspects of development (Rositi et al., 2022). Art education for early childhood cannot be equated with others (Amalia & Agustin, 2022). In early childhood art education, the aim is not to produce children as artists, because successful learning does not make children successful as singers, musicians or dancers. The success of teaching art to children is that children can become individuals who are more sensitive both to themselves and the environment (Sandra Devindriati Kusuma et al., 2022). This is also supported by the presentation which states that art for early childhood contains a deeper function, namely prioritizing the ability to express oneself so that children can communicate what their thoughts are (Gunada, 2022). Therefore, there is a need for art learning in early childhood.

Art learning materials for early childhood are made based on children's characteristics (Nugraheni & Pamungkas, 2022). This statement is strengthened by the assumption that through arts education that is appropriate to one's age and characteristics, in the learning process, one's intellectual intelligence will equally develop along with emotional and spiritual intelligence (Gunada, 2022). Moreover, in art learning, it is also important to learn art from a cultural perspective (Miranti et al., 2021). Many researchers have presented the results of findings in relevant research regarding art learning both cultural and religious elements. One of them is research (Sunarti et al., 2021) which explains the cultural elements in the folklore Komerling Seharuk. In this research, we succeeded in describing four elements of Komerling culture, namely the use of Komerling language, regional songs, the setting of the Komerling river, and Tala Balak. Meanwhile, research (Kirana et al., 2022) explains the religious elements in the film Assalamualaikum Beijing about literature learning in high school. The religious elements are explained by explaining the content of religious values in the film. Through the content of existing religious values, it can improve the quality of drama learning (Kirana et al., 2022).

Early childhood education institutions in the Special Region of Yogyakarta include schools located in places of worship. Such as the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten which is in the Church Area in the Turi Sleman Area, and the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten which is in the Yogyakarta Syuhada Mosque Yard. These two kindergartens have different religious backgrounds, namely Christianity and Islam. Judging from the religious background, the two institutions will provide different forms of learning, especially in the arts. The art learning in both schools applies art learning with a religious basis. These two institutions have used an independent curriculum in implementing classroom learning. Therefore, this research will discuss cultural and religious elements in children's art learning at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and the

Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten with the latest curriculum guide, namely independent learning. The limitations of this research are only related to cultural and religious elements in art learning at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten.

METHOD

The method for conducting this research is qualitative research methods. Where this research was carried out using triangulation of data sources. Data collection was carried out by observation, interviews with teachers and school principals, and implementation of documentation (Yin, 2011). Data analysis contains cultural and religious elements that exist in art learning at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. Art Learning at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten

The art learning at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten consists of several areas of art material, namely music, fine arts, both two-dimensional and three-dimensional and dance. The art learning here is created and adapted for children. Below are the types of art at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten from various fields of artistic activities.

a. Art Learning Materials

The material given to children in art learning here will be divided into three parts, namely the areas of music, fine arts and dance. In the musical arts at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten, there are activities to improve sound arts skills and musical instrument playing skills. This sound arts activity is carried out by the school in choir activities. Apart from that, before learning begins, this kindergarten also carries out activities to sing Indonesia Raya and Mars TK Indriyasana every day. To support musical arts skills, the school also provides facilities and activities for playing drum band and angklung as a means of supporting children's music. There are two types of learning activities in fine arts, namely two-dimensional fine arts such as drawing, making mosaics, collages, batik, and others. Meanwhile, this three-dimensional art activity is carried out by making sculptures from plasticine. There are also dance activities at school which are carried out during dance lessons by teachers from dance experts outside the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten institution. The dances taught are the jaranan dance and the hat dance.

b. Development of Art Materials

The development of art materials is carried out by adapting school conditions to the background of religious-based schools. At Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten, he carries out art activities which are developed into learning activities using art. The following is the artistic development carried out.

1) Sing the song Mars TK Indriyasana Somoitan

Every day before learning activities begin, children are invited to sing the song Indonesia Raya and the Mars song TK Indriyasana Somoitan. Based on the results of the interview, this can increase enthusiasm and love for their nation and school. This feeling can arise with stimulation through the songs taught.

2) Use of tone in prayer

Apart from loving the homeland and school, Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten also invites children to love God by always praying before activities start. This prayer habit also includes elements of art by giving a tone when saying "In the name of the Father, in the name of the Son, and in the Holy Spirit, amen amen". This can make children conditioned and easy to get used to praying calmly.

3) Sing traditional children's songs

Before the play activity, the children were invited to sing traditional children's songs such as the song Gundul-gundul Pacul, Yen Esuk Sugeng Enjing, and the song Aku Duwe Pitik Cilik. This song is sung at the wish of the child. Children can choose what song to sing.

4) Apperception with songs

During the observation, the learning topic at that time was work, then the teacher invited the children to find out what kinds of work there were. The teacher asks the children about this by making guesses with the song "The police are asking questions, just a moment. In the name of work. Starting from (mentioning the child's name)." In sequence, children will name the jobs they know.

5) Spiritual Song Choir

The children's choir at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten is trained by the teacher. The songs taught are mostly spiritual songs that are usually sung in church. An example of a song taught is a song amidst the waves. The Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten choir often collaborates with the church at Christmas.

6) Playing Angklung at church

The angklung game at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten teaches regional, national and children's songs and spiritual songs are still taught. The angklung team at this school is also often displayed at the church at certain events.

7) Fine arts activities based on religious stories

Art learning for children can be done by telling stories first before carrying out activities. This is implemented by schools when creating works for children that begin with telling stories. This activity can encourage children to imagine what is being told. As in the activity of making statues with plasticine, the teacher gives a story about Adam and Eve. Then at the end of the story, after questions and answers, children are invited to make a statue of Adam and Eve from the plasticine that has been provided.

Figure 1. The teacher tells a story before the children are invited to express their art

8) Offering Dance

The development of dance learning at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten is still on a religious basis. Dance learning at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten is displayed at the Church by performing the Offering Dance.

To support the vision and mission of becoming a cultural school, Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten wears traditional Javanese clothing every Thursday because art and culture are closely related. Then, children and teachers at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten are active in church activities, especially every Sunday. This involvement between schools and churches is unique because art learning can be developed together with religion.

c. Art learning at the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten

a. Art Learning Materials

The art learning at the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten is more about extracurricular learning. In the art of music, there is learning about angklung and gamelan. Meanwhile, in sound art, there is singing. In the movement arts, there is dance and in the fine arts, there is making mosaics, coloring, batik and extra painting. This art learning material, especially in extracurricular activities, is carried out by looking for teachers from outside the school. However, there is one extra, namely Painting, where the teacher becomes an extra Painting teacher. Extra planning, at the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten does not provide extra materials to teachers, and vice versa. Evaluation of art learning at the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten is by looking at the extent to which children are interested in extracurricular activities. Then, according to the results of interviews with the school principal, the children found this extra gamelan the most difficult. Then in the learning system, extra teachers provide reports on the results of extracurricular activities by providing extra assessments for children to their respective class teachers.

Figure 2. Children's activities playing gamelan

a. Development of Art Materials

The art material taught to children can be carried out with various kinds of development. At the Syudhada Mosque Kindergarten, which is located in the religious area of the mosque building, it is possible to combine art learning with religion. What is also interesting is that art is associated with religion. The Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten uses art when praying. In prayer activities, children use tones to memorize prayers using the umami reading method. This can be seen in the words of an interview with the school principal regarding singing music lessons, children are taught songs with religious nuances such as the songs "Alhamdulillah" and prayers. Apart from sound art activities, artistic development is also carried out in the art of gamelan music which collaborates between schools and gamelan trainers to provide sholawat music using this traditional Javanese musical instrument. However, in the gamelan extra, Javanese songs are also taught. In extra dancing, children are also taught not only Javanese dance but also dance or movement and songs with Islamic songs such as the song "Barakallah". Apart from extracurricular activities, activities in class are also related to religion. This is like during the environmental love project activity in the use of used goods, in Yunus' class he made prayer beads from used newspapers. This aims to realize the vision and mission of the school.

Figure 3. Children's work making prayer beads from old newspapers

The uniqueness of the institution in developing art learning at the Syuhada Mosque is that in developing this art, it adheres to one principle, namely adapting to the religion one adheres to. Various artistic activities can all be related to religious topics. This is in line with the school's vision mission and

characteristics. However, the learning carried out does not leave behind the existing culture and educational developments.

DISCUSSION

The statements from observations, interviews and documentation above show that Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten provides art lessons to children using elements of the Catholic religion such as stories in books, spiritual songs, prayers and introduction to religious holidays. At the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten, art learning is applied using an Islamic religious background with an introduction to prayer, Islamic songs, tools for worship, and commemoration of Islamic religious days. The two activities carried out look the same but the implementation of the activities is different.

According to the results of the observation data, it can be seen that there are several religious and cultural elements in art learning in the two schools above. Culture needs to be preserved, namely by applying it in everyday life (Amalia & Agustin, 2022). In the world of education, this can be done as in these two schools which apply culture in arts learning. The cultural elements that emerge can be learning systems, language and behavior (Permatasari et al., 2020). In the activities at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten, learning is implemented with cultural elements, such as during extracurricular learning and in classroom learning activities. Children are taught to play angklung, which is a traditional musical instrument. Then the children are also introduced to regional songs and games. Apart from that, children are also introduced to typical regional fabrics and traditional clothing.

Based on the results of the explanation above, can be presented in table form to see the differences in art learning in these two schools in more detail and concisely. The following is a comparative table of art learning at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten based on the classification of cultural and religious elements.

Table 1. Comparison table of art learning at Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten based on classification of cultural and religious elements

No	Classification	TK Indriyasana Somoitan	TK Masjid Syuhada
1	Religious Elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use of tone in prayer b. Sing spiritual songs before play activities c. Choir of spiritual songs d. Playing angklung performing at church e. Drawing on 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use of tone in prayer (Ummi method) b. Sing religious songs before play activities c. Singing Islamic songs performing in the mosque d. Playing gamelan with prayer songs.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> religious themes f. Decorate the Christmas tree g. Make a plasticine figurine from the story of Adan and Eve h. Performing a sacrificial dance at church 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e. Carrying out religious theme projects (Islamic themed pictures, making prayer beads from old newspapers, making religious posters, even holding parades). f. Performing the Barakallah song dance at the mosque
2	Cultural elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Angklung extracurricular b. Introduction to traditional dance c. Singing children's folk songs d. Batik e. Traditional clothing during art lessons every Thursday 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Angklung extracurricular b. Gamelan extracurricular c. Introduction to traditional dance d. Batik

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the role of religious and cultural elements can become interesting art learning materials for children. This is because learning that is adapted to the child's characteristics can increase the attractiveness of learning (Hendraningrat & Fauziah, 2021). Based on previous research, there is a statement that 96.7% of parents choose schools based on learning by providing religious elements (Nadia Sari, 2019). According to this research, art learning can be linked to religious elements. Learning art with religious elements can increase religious knowledge and using cultural elements is a form of preserving culture from an early age. One of the findings in this research is that cultural elements in art learning which are collaborated with religious elements are things that can build the quality of learning in a school. This is the same as in the two kindergartens which is a characteristic of learning there. So that religious and cultural elements can be collaborated in early childhood art learning, especially at the Insriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and the Syuhada Mosque Kindergarten.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the observations above, it can be concluded that the activities at the Indriyasana Somoitan Kindergarten and the Syuhada Mosque

Kindergarten have different characteristics in the development of art. However, both schools have similarities in art learning which is related to art for early childhood. The religious elements that appear in art learning in both kindergartens are religious stories, religious singing, prayer activities with tunes, projects through stories in books, dance with religious songs, playing angklung with spiritual songs, and playing gamelan with religious songs such as prayers. Meanwhile, the cultural elements that are applied are the introduction of traditional musical instruments, the introduction of traditional dance, the singing of children's songs, the use of traditional games associated with learning, making batik, and using traditional clothing in art learning.

References

Adini, E. Y., Hasanah, N., & Oktaviyanti, I. (2022). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran MAPENA (Mainan Peta Anak) pada Materi IPS untuk Siswa Kelas IV SDN 39 Mataram. *Jurnal Ilmiah Profesi Pendidikan*, 7(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jipp.v7i1.386>

Amalia, N. A., & Agustin, D. (2022). Peranan Pusat Seni dan Budaya sebagai Bentuk Upaya Pelestarian Budaya Lokal. *Sinektika: Jurnal Arsitektur*, 19(1), 34–40. <https://doi.org/10.23917/sinektika.v19i1.13707>

Eka Retnaningsih, L., & Patilima, S. (2022). Kurikulum merdeka pada pendidikan anak usia dini. *Jurnal Program Studi PGRA*, 8(1), 143–158. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.29062/seling.v8i2.1223>

Gunada, I. W. A. (2022). Konsep, Fungsi Dan Strategi Pembelajaran Seni Bagi Peserta Didik Usia Dini. *Kumarottama: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 1(2), 109–123. <https://doi.org/10.53977/kumarottama.v1i2.383>

Hendraningrat, D., & Fauziah, P. (2021). Media Pembelajaran Digital untuk Stimulasi Motorik Halus Anak Usia Dini. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(1), 58–72. <https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v6i1.1205>

Kirana, A., Abadiah, E. N., Putri, H. W. R., & Musyarafah, N. Al. (2022). Analisis Unsur Religius Dalam Film Assalamualaikum Beijing Pembelajaran Sastra Di Sma. 1, 497–506.

Miranti, A., Lilik, L., Winarni, R., & Surya, A. (2021). Representasi Pendidikan Karakter Berbasis Kearifan Lokal dalam Motif Batik Wahyu Ngawiyatan sebagai Muatan Pendidikan Senirupa di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(2), 546–560. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v5i2.763>

Nadia Sari, dan N. S. (2019). Survei Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Pertimbangan Orangtua Dalam Pemilihan Taman Kanak-Kanak (TK) di Kota Surabaya. *Paper Knowledge . Toward a Media History of Documents*, 1–6.

Nugraheni, T., & Pamungkas, J. (2022). Analisis Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Seni Pada PAUD. *Early Childhood Research Journal (ECRJ)*, 5(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.23917/ecrj.v5i1.18689>

Permatasari, A. S. N., Nugraha, S. ri, & Widharyanto, B. (2020). Analisis unsur budaya dalam buku ajar BIPA Agmi. *Jurnal Bahasa Indonesia Bagi Penutur Asing (JBIPA)*, 2(1), 22–27. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26499/jbipa.v4i1.4972>

Rositi, R., Anggraini, H., & Sulistianah, S. (2022). Dinamika perilaku berbagi anak usia dini di tk tunas kusuma bandar lampung tahun pelajaran 2021/2022. *Early Childhood Research ...*, 1(1), 1–8. <https://jurnal.unived.ac.id/index.php/ecrp/article/view/1949>

Sandra Devindriati Kusuma, P., Made Dian Widiastuti, N., & Iriani, W. (2022). Musik dan Gerak: Pendidikan Seni bagi Anak Usia Dini. *Journal of Music Science, Technology, and Industry*, 5(1), 85–95. <https://jurnal.isi-dps.ac.id/index.php/jomsti/>

Sunarti, I., Febriyanto, D., & Widodo, M. (2021). Unsur Budaya Dan Nilai Moral Dalam Cerita Rakyat Komerling Seharuk: Sebuah Tinjauan Sosiologi Sastra. *Widyaparwa*, 49(2), 387–401. <https://doi.org/10.26499/wdprw.v49i2.898>

Yin, R. K. (2011). Qualitative reasearch from start to finish. In *Guilford* (Vol. 44, Issue 8). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1751-8113/44/8/085201>